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Educational Approaches to Combating Security Challenges in Nigeria

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Abstract

Insecurity is a state of lack of security, it is a prominent challenge facing Nigeria as a nation. This paper finds out educational approaches to combating security challenges in Nigeria. Three research questions were formulated to guide the study. Descriptive survey design was adopted for the study. 40 lecturers and 160 students of four tertiary institutions were sampled using proportionate stratified random sampling technique. The research instrument named "Questionnaire on Educational Approaches to Combating Security Challenges in Nigeria" (QEACSCN) was used for data collection. The data collected were analysed using mean and standard deviation to answer the research questions. The findings showed that there are various national security challenges such as kidnapping, robbery, killing, bombing, among others with its causes as unemployment, bribery and corruption, economic factor, ethnic differences, illiteracy and religious factors are the major factors contributing to insecurity in the Nigeria society. Based on the findings of the study, it was recommended among others that the government should put in place the necessary educational programmes which will make citizens more useful and self-reliant, such as vocational education, rural education and mass media education.

Keywords: Educational Approaches, Combating, Security, Challenges.

INTRODUCTION

In the recent years, insecurity remains one of the frontal challenges facing Nigeria and most of the prominent African nations, among other nations of the world. This colossal quandary remains a clog in the wheel of both the economic, political and social development of the nation Nigeria. As a result of this, it has also received the attention of numerous researchers. Insecurity issues in various African countries no doubt have roots in the failure of the government policies to provide or manage the basic human physiological needs of their citizens. In recent times, Nigeria has witnessed increasing number of security challenges that constitute threats to the cooperate, existence of its citizens and to the maintenance and survival of its democratic political system. These security challenges are diverse and complex, ranging from political disagreements to criminal activities with alarming dimensions and consequences.

According to Oshio (2009), the concept of security is not alien and has been central even in the primitive societies. The need for security necessitated the social contract in which people willingly surrendered their rights to an organ (government) who oversees the survival of all. For decades, issues relating to security tend to occupy the centre stage in the development discourse. With the end of the cold war, there have been attempts to shift conceptualization of security from a state-centric perspective to a broader view that places premium on individuals, in which human security that embodies elements of national security, human rights and national development remain major barometer for explaining the concept. At the heart of this debate there have been attempts to deepen and widen the concept of security from the level of the states to societies and individuals, and from military to non-military issues (Krahmann, 2013).

Security is considered as any mechanism deliberately fashioned to alleviate the most serious and immediate threats that prevent people from pursuing their cherished values. Olaitan (2017) said that in an ideal and well governed state, there is a symbiotic relationship between education and security. Insecurity undermines education and absence or poor quality education for citizens constitute a constraint on capacity for sustainable security in multifaceted dimensions encapsulated in human security framework.

Education is critical for promoting sustainable development and improving the capacity of the people to address environment and development issues. Both formal and non-formal educations are indispensable to changing people's attitudes so that they have the capacity to assess and address their sustainable development concerns. It is also critical for achieving environmental and ethical awareness, values and attitudes, skills and behaviour consistent with sustainable development and for effective public participation in decision making.

A liberal education is one that frees the minds of its recipients from their preconceptions. It broadens the possibilities for greater understanding of others in our nation and around the world (Forum Futures, 2007). Institutions should try to train future workers to help States' economies and to offer liberal education so as to produce informed citizens who can contribute to our democratic way of life.

Every independent and sovereign state must train, sustain and nurture men and women to serve in its security and intelligence outfits. According to Ehi (2009), in Europe and America, these men and women are selected from the best and the brightest citizens, who are endowed with keen and subtle intellect. Education helps to create informed citizenry which is vital to our democratic society. It increases the potential for individuals to perform as citizens. There are many examples of the public being misinformed and making bad decisions. However, without education, the situation would be vastly worse. It gives one the ability to critically examine an issue and articulate a reasoned position about it. Nurturing critical thinking is a key component of education. Hence, the essence of this paper is to investigate and point out various educational approaches which can be adopted to combat security challenges in Nigeria

Problem Statement

It is no longer a news that the state of insecurity in Nigeria is highly disheartening, there is no longer freedom from danger or threats, and the ability of a nation to protect and develop itself. General peace and security in any society is associated with lack of violence, absence of civil disorder and insurgency to mention but a few. In the general terms, there are also security challenges from food, water and health. National security starts with the social security component as represented by health care, food, and shelter and clothing. The worsening economic conditions have been generating a mix of domestic, social and political tension. Governments are often expected to provide their citizens with political stability and socio-economic security including health care, adequate protection of lives and properties and shelter. Lack of these basics often breeds discontents and social unrest which is the current state of Nigeria. Therefore, there is a need to find out the educational approaches that can be adopted to combat security challenges in Nigeria.

Purpose of the Study

The main purpose of this study is to investigate educational approaches to combating security challenges in Nigeria. Specifically the study seeks to;

- i. Identify the factors contributing to insecurity in the Nigeria society,
- ii. Find out various educational approaches that can be adopted in combating insecurity in the Nigeria society, and
- iii. Find out the roles played by education in promoting security in Nigeria.

Research Questions

The following three research questions were formulated to guide the study;

- i. What are the factors contributing to insecurity in the Nigeria society?

- ii. What are the various educational approaches that can be adopted in combating insecurity in Nigeria society?
- iii. What are the roles played by education in promoting security?

LITERATURE REVIEW

Concept of Security

The concept of security had being widely defined by several authorities, this ranges from individuals in journal, research reports, news papers, among others. Adejumo (2011), the term security was stated to be an act of keeping peace within the governing territories. This is usually done by upholding the national law and defending the internal security threats in different areas of the country. Not only this, according to Nwagboso, (2012) is the act of being safe from harm or danger, the defense, protection and preservation of values, and the absence of threats to acquired values. Security is about survival and the condition of human existence. Security also exists when people live together in a certain environment without disturbance or violent.

Based on the above various views, security can therefore be said to be an act of seeing the survival of all and sundry in the society. It is the search to avoid, prevent, reduce, or resolve violence and conflict in any society. Usually, general peace and security in any society is associated with lack of violence, absence of civil disorder and insurgency to mention but a few. In the general terms, there are also security challenges from food, water and health. National security starts with the social security component as represented by health care, food, and shelter and clothing. The worsening economic conditions have been generating a mix of domestic, social and political tension. Governments are often expected to provide their citizens with political stability and socio-economic security including health care, adequate protection of lives and properties and shelter. Lack of these basics often breeds discontents and social unrest.

Causes of Insecurity in Nigeria

We cannot really combat insecurity without looking into its root causes, the cause of insecurity in Nigeria according to Okereke (2012) can be distinguished among the following factors;

Bribery and Corruption

Bribery and corruption according to Fukuyama (2004) is one of the major problems confronting Nigeria economy. Most people that occupy strategic positions in the administration of this country take advantage of their positions to loot the treasure of the government without query of molestation. In fact, most of them embezzle through inflated contracts to an increasing army of party loyalists who have neither the desire nor the competence to execute their contracts, to over invoicing, consumption of escalating salaries of grossly over-staffed and unproductive public servant and a host of others without queries or harassment. This type of practice have made some elites to believe that justice can be bought or sold in this country depending on one's bargaining power, Nwadiolor (2011)

Economic Factors

Iygeal (2012) also states that some individuals in Nigeria are power-brokers and are stronger than the government. They see themselves as untouchables and boast about themselves. Even if contracts are awarded to them in any part of the country, such contracts are paid for without execution. Likewise because of personal aggrandizement, some political office holders award contracts to themselves without execution. This attitude leads to wasteful resources by the government. Sometimes if the government uses force on them to return such money embezzled using law enforcement agents like the Police, Economic & Financial Crimes Commission

(EFCC), Independent Corrupt Practices Commission (ICPC) etc, permission and clearance or permission "have to be obtained from their so-called godfathers or powerful individual involved (Onouha2011) . Likewise,

unscrupulous money-bags and criminals are celebrated because of their wealth without asking how and where the wealth is acquired (Olaitan 2017). This behaviour results to a lot of wasteful resources in the country.

Internal Security Disorder

Internal security rest on the authority of interior minister and defense minister in the federation. They are to initiate and supervise the mode of operation by the police and other security agents in the country to ensure that peace and harmonious living exist in every nooks and crannies of the country. More so, in different states and local government areas of this country, the political office holders as the security officers are to maintain and sustain the security situation in their territory. This can be done by making sure that the law enforcement agencies deployed to their areas do their work diligently. However, in most cases, many of these security agents according to Iygeal (2012) sometimes seem to be ignorant of what is happening around them but depend on information from the general public before there action. Sometimes, some of them may hear about violence and criminal activities but for the fear of death may neglect their action resulting to security disorder by some security agents in the country. Usually, this type of security disorder is very disastrous to the security situation in the country.

Poor System of Governance

In any economy, government activities are expected to agree with norms and aspirations of the people within the area of governance. This is because, for effective administration to take place, government is challenged to focus attention mostly on programmes and policies that have direct bearing on the teaming population. However, more often than not, some political office holders use to neglect their promises during campaign after being elected into power and concentrate on activities that can enriches their pockets. This poor attitude and negligence, often results to anger among people and leads to insecurity in many part of the country (Iygeal 2012). Also, most of the government functions are concentrated at the seat of the government which is usually in the headquarters either of the federal, state or local governments. In this case, high security may be maintained in the center while people living in the hinterland are left with little or no protection. This according to Nwagboso (2012) can create a lot of security threat to the hinterland.

Weak Judicial System and Injustice

Most people commit all manner of crimes and get away with it scot- free. For instance, a rich man or some people in high authority can commit a lot of atrocity and get away with it because of nepotism and impunity but ordinary person is punished for a trivial offense. This type of favouritism in Nigeria legal system is detrimental to professionalism of legal practice for better service delivery (Okorie 2011).

Religious Fanatics

Most religious groups in Nigeria both Islamic and Christian religion preaches peace and unity but some religious extremist believe that violence and destruction is the only way to achieve heaven. Good example of this set is BokoHaram insurgency. Current and general state of insecurity in most part of the country today is weighted to different report of BokoHaram (Ezeoha 2011).

Ethnic Differences

Majority of the insecurity issues, clashes, violence and killing occurring in most areas in Nigeria can be linked up with ethnic differences in Nigeria. According to research, Nigeria is made up of over 200 ethnic groups, most of which are minority groups, as a result of this, ethnic differences pose a lot of problem to the Nigerian nation. Bello (2012), in his view noted that starting with the usual religious/ethnic oriented conflicts, to the Jos ethnic/religious/political conflict of 2008, regrettably, the Northern states have shown that security of persons and properties is still far from being secured.

Illiteracy

Another cause of insecurity in Nigeria is illiteracy, Nigeria has several illiterates who shun the western education and this renders them intellectually handicapped. This is more of the cause of insecurity in the Northern part of Nigeria, there are elements of theocratic opinionated ambitions in the current crisis which

started in Bauchi and engulfed other states in the North. This is so because the demand by the fundamentalist groups BokoHaram's for the removal of western behavioural pattern may have been masterminded by some unscrupulous elements in the country which is ridiculous to the entire nation, this is triggered by illiteracy and ignorance.

Apart from the socio-economic security challenges, Ehi, (2009) identified some of the major security challenges confronting the nation to include political and electioneering conflicts, ethno-religious crises, ethnic militias, boundary disputes, cultism, criminality and organized crimes.

In the same vein, Oshio (2009) opined that Nigeria is today plagued with social disorder, insecurity, poverty, illiteracy, balance of payment deficit, poor health statistics, ethnic and religious conflicts, corruption, crime and criminality and political crises. All these mean that we are very insecure in terms of human wellbeing. The problems, individually and collectively constitute threats to the peace, security and development of the country. Invariably, they have implications for the continuity and survival of the nation's nascent democracy.

Instances of Security Challenges in Nigeria

Security challenges in Contemporary Nigeria is currently plagued by different forms of insecurity that need to be tackled in order to promote and protect human security and development as well as national integration, security and development. Some of the major security challenges are:

Widespread cases of violent crimes, especially armed robbery and kidnapping, instances of this includes the Offa bank robbery case of 2018, Ido-Ani bank robbery case of 2019, numerous kidnapping issues which happened mostly in south-western states of recent. Widespread problem of corruption that affect the ability of the country and her citizens to enjoy personal security and development, widespread incidence of ethnic and religious violence and terrorism across the country. Widespread conflict between Fulani herdsmen and farmers resulting in frequent killings, destruction of villages and settlements, and internal displacement of victims in different parts of the country.

Political and election related violence, an instance of the numerous election violence in Lagos and Rivers states which happened in the recently concluded 2019 general elections Destruction of critical infrastructure (vandalization of oils and gas pipelines, electricity grids and facilities, educational and health facilities, setting offices onfire, etc.) by individual criminals, ethno-religious militias, and criminal groups and the theft of critical national resources such as illegal mining, illegal bunkering.

Nnadi, (2016) noted in her study that Nigeria is faced with numerous security challenges. Some of the security challenges insurgency of the Niger Delta Militants, Corruption, Political assassinations, incessant bloody violence of the National Union of Road Transport Workers (NURTW), BokoHaram upsurge, communal violence, electoral violence, youth militancy, ethnic militants, among others. The activities of the various organized groups include; threat to the peace of the Nigerian polity, co-operate existence of Nigeria and introduction of Nigerians to suicide bombing. These emphasize some of the security challenges faced in Nigeria.

Effects of Insecurity on the Nigerian Society

Insecurity which used to be one of the lowest concerns in the hierarchy of Nigeria's social problems has now assumed an alarming proportion. This is because insecurity is like a sore in a man's lap which if not well treated expands gradually to the man's waist. This may have been the reason while the case of insecurity at present is very difficult to handle thereby costing the government a lot of money. However, the effects of insecurity according to Tella (2012) include the loss of life and material resources. The results of insecurity since the past few years according to human Rights Watch has been so alarming. From security monitoring agency report, between 2009 and 2018, over 6,800 lives had been lost to insurgencies. Also, within the first nine months in 2012, 815 people were killed in 275 suspected attacks, and more than 60 police stations were attacked in 10 Northern states, excluding the bomb of the police headquarters in Abuja (Adejumo 2011).

The data base of orphans and widows caused by the rampaging sects has grown rapidly. Because of this, Money from some international organization and funds raised locally by the governments, non-governmental agencies, charitable organizations and individuals which are supposed to be channeled to human capital development have been deployed to the rehabilitation of families of the casualties and the renovation of properties destroyed by the insurgences thereby causing a huge loss of revenue to the government (Adejumo, (2011).

Consequently, the activities of these various militia groups has resulted to low income for government from oil revenue, moderating the Gross Domestic Product growth rate, low participation of local and foreign investors in economic development and insecurity of lives and properties of the citizens.

Educational Approaches towards Combating Insecurity

Over the years, it has being discovered that many conflicts arise from ignorance and manipulation of ethnic and religious identity. Education, not mere schooling, produce tolerant and civil citizens who are able to understand and live with people from different economic, religious, ethnic and cultural backgrounds and other forms of identities.

Most people arrested for criminal behaviours lack high education which often influence their criminality; their vulnerability to living conditions that subject them to intensive surveillance; their inability to avoid detection, arrest, trial and conviction. Paradoxically, persons with low education and income are more likely to be victims of crime and other forms of insecurity.

Education has been defined as a process by which individuals are assisted formally through proper direction and guidance to develop their capacities for their own benefit and that of the society (Ehi, 2009). It is geared towards developing the individuals for them to live effectively and efficiently in the society and to contribute to its advancement and upliftment. Hence, through education the behaviour patterns of the citizens could be changed in the desired direction. In other words, with sound education people will start to understand and appreciate one another better and try to restore the dignity of man. For instance, the introduction of vocational education, mass media education, rural education, adult education and entrepreneurship programmes into the curriculum at the various levels of education in Nigeria is a welcome innovation that goes a long way to strengthening the popular liberal education.

It is also no news that graduates of our institutions of higher learning have been populating the crime world due to their inability to secure meaningful employment upon graduation. This scenario calls for the intensification of the emphasis on vocational, mass media education, rural education, adult education and entrepreneurial education to equip graduates with occupational survival skills - to be able to identify and even create and exploit investment opportunities that abound in the society. The present global economic crises and rising waves of unemployment have greatly emphasized the need for functional entrepreneurship and vocational education.

Also, there is also the need to introduce Nigerian History, moral and civic education into the curriculum. Graduates should actually be found worthy first in character and then in learning. Every youth should see himself/herself as a stakeholder in the Nigerian project, by exercising all requisite citizenship roles and responsibilities. It should be inculcated in our children at the early age the respect for human life and the dignity of labour. Civic education will place youth on a sound pedestal to defend our nascent democracy instead of being destructive agents. A poor knowledge of our national history will hinder informed citizenry which is required for rapid development of the nation.

Roles played by Education in Promoting Security in Nigeria

Education has earlier been defined as a process by which individuals are assisted formally through proper direction and guidance to develop their capacities for their own benefits and that of the society. It therefore follows, by a simple logic, that if a nation bequeaths the right type of education to its citizens, the citizens will not turn against their father- land. Daily Sun (2013) recently reported the former minister of

Education, Professor Rukayat Rufai as having identified reform of the education system as the solution to the security challenges confronting the nation.

There is need for a total overhaul of the curriculum at all levels of education with a view to providing its recipients, broad based education in the development of the mind, soul and body; and in comprehending the environment and in the development of appropriate attitudes, skills, abilities and competences to co-exist with and contribute to the development of the society. This calls for a synergy between liberal education, vocational and entrepreneurship education.

A liberal education is one that frees the minds of its recipients from their preconceptions. It broadens the possibilities for greater understanding of others in our nation and around the world (Forum Futures, 2007). Institutions should try to train future workers to help states economies and to offer liberal education so as to produce informed citizens who can contribute to our democratic way of life.

Education helps to create informed citizenry which is vital to our democratic society. It increases the potential for individuals to perform as citizens. There are many examples of the public being misinformed and making bad decisions. However, without education, the situation would be vastly worse. It gives one the ability to critically examine an issue and articulate a reasoned position about it. Nurturing critical thinking is a key component of education. National security cannot be narrowed down to defense and military might alone. It is wider than that. It is this narrow conception of national security that forms the basis for the disproportionate budgetary allocation of funds as the case is, to "ensure the security of lives and property", however, to the utter neglect of other equally important sectors of the economy that bear directly or indirectly on national security.

Oshio (2009) observed that the fundamental objectives and directive principles of state policy under the 1999 constitution of Nigeria contain many social- economic and political rights which, if fully implemented, would go a long way towards ensuring national security and development. These rights, he went further to state, are comparable to the economic, social and cultural right adopted by the United Nations General Assembly in 1966. Despite availability of resources the Nigeria State has failed to take necessary steps to give effect to these rights.

Methodology

This research adopted survey research design, this method paved way for the use of a self-structured questionnaire which was used as an instrument for data gathering. The instrument which is a questionnaire titled "Questionnaire on Educational Approaches to Combating Security Challenges in Nigeria" (QEACSCN). Two hundred copies of the research questionnaires were made and administered on two hundred respondents randomly selected from four tertiary institutions. The four tertiary institutions were randomly selected from Ondo State. The population consists of lecturers and students. The study area is Ondo State, which is one of the six states within the southwest geo-political zone of Nigeria. It is considered that whatsoever operates within the area used operates across the whole states of the nation. The data analysis method adopted is mean and standard deviation.

Results

Two hundred respondents were pre-dominantly used in this study, they were randomly sampled from four tertiary institutions. Forty lecturers and one hundred and sixty students were involved in the study, ten lecturers and forty students were randomly picked from each of the four tertiary institutions used.

Research Question One: What are the factors contributing to insecurity in the Nigeria society?

Table 1: Mean ratings and standard deviations on the factors contributing to insecurity in the Nigeria society.

Item No	Item Description	S	A	A	D	S	D	\bar{X}	ST.D	Decision		
1	. Unemployment	6	1	8	8	1	9	3	2	2.89	1.02	Agreed
2	. Bribery and Corruption	7	2	7	8	1	8	3	2	2.95	1.05	Agreed
3	. Economic factor	8	4	6	7	2	9	2	0	3.01	0.98	Agreed
4	. Ethnic-differences	5	2	1	1	1	8	1	9	2.98	0.86	Agreed
5	. Illiteracy	6	3	7	9	1	8	4	0	2.83	1.01	Agreed
6	. Religious factor	3	6	7	1	6	3	3	0	2.57	0.95	Agreed

Table 1 reveals that the mean ratings of items 1-6 are 2.61, 2.95, 3.01, 2.98, 2.83 and 2.57, that are greater than 2.50, with the corresponding standard deviations of 1.02, 1.05, 0.98, 0.86, 1.01 and 0.95 respectively. This implies that unemployment, bribery and corruption, economic factor, ethnic differences, illiteracy and religious factors are the major factors contributing to insecurity in the Nigeria society.

Research Question Two: What are the various educational approaches that can be adopted in combating insecurity in Nigeria society?

Table 2: Mean ratings and standard deviations on the various educational approaches that can be adopted in combating insecurity in Nigeria society

Item No	Item Description	S	A	A	D	S	D	\bar{X}	ST.D	Decision		
7	. Vocational Educational	3	2	8	9	4	8	3	1	2.61	0.93	Agreed
8	. Mass Media Education	4	8	8	1	5	3	1	8	2.80	0.91	Agreed
9	. Rural Education	6	2	9	7	2	0	2	1	3.00	0.91	Agreed
10	. Adult Education	6	1	8	0	4	0	2	0	2.90	0.90	Agreed

Table 2 reveals that the mean ratings of items 7-10 are 2.61, 2.80, 3.00 and 2.90 respectively that are greater than 2.50, with the corresponding standard deviations of 0.93, 0.91, 0.91 and 0.90. This implies that vocational education, mass media education, rural and adult educations are major educational approaches that can be adopted in combating insecurity in the Nigeria society.

Research Question 3: What are the roles played by education in promoting security?

Table 3: Mean ratings and standard deviations on the roles played by education in promoting security

Item No	Item Description	S	A	A	D	S	D	\bar{X}	ST.D	Decision		
11	. Educational programmes enlightens citizen on dangers involved in insecurity.	4	4	6	7	6	8	2	1	2.67	0.94	Agreed
12	. Educational skills makes citizen useful and self reliance.	6	3	7	9	1	8	4	0	2.83	1.01	Agreed
13	. Educational programme exposes citizens to the knowledge of societal developmental in goals.	3	6	7	1	6	3	3	0	2.57	0.95	Agreed
14	. Educational programmes like NYSC fosters unity within the Nigerian society.	2	5	1	0	6	0	1	5	2.68	0.79	Agreed
15	. Educational programmes helps to reduce crime within the society.	7	2	7	8	1	8	3	2	2.95	1.05	Agreed

Table 3 above shows that the mean ratings of items 11-15 are 2.67, 2.83, 2.57, 2.68 and 2.95 respectively, which are greater than 2.50, with the corresponding standard deviations of 0.94, 1.01, 0.95, 0.79 and 1.05 respectively. This means that the respondents agreed that educational programmes enlightens citizen on dangers involved in insecurity, educational skills makes citizen useful and self-reliance, educational programme exposes citizens to the knowledge of societal developmental in goals, educational programmes like

NYSC fosters unity within the Nigerian society and they also agreed that educational programmes helps to reduce crime within the society.

Discussion

This study revealed that unemployment, bribery and corruption, economic factor, ethnic differences, illiteracy and religious factors are the major factors contributing to insecurity in the Nigeria society. This is in agreement with a study carried out by Fukuyama (2004) who reported that bribery and corruption is one of the major problems confronting Nigeria security as most people that occupy strategic positions in the administration of this country take advantage of their positions to loot the treasure of the government without query of molestation, this hinders the nations' development. Also, unemployment and illiteracy coupled with ethnic and religious factors are causal factors of insecurity in Nigeria, as pointed out by Ezeoha (2011) stating that some religious extremist believe that violence and destruction is the only way to achieve heaven. Good example of this set is BokoHaram insurgency. Bello (2012) also pointed out that starting with the usual religious/ethnic oriented conflicts, to the Jos ethnic/religious/political conflict of 2008, regrettably, the Northern states have shown that security of persons and properties is still far from being secured. Apart from the above, Ehi, (2009) identified some of the major security challenges confronting the nation to include political and electioneering conflicts, ethno-religious crises, ethnic militias, boundary disputes, cultism, criminality and organized crimes.

This study revealed that vocational education, mass media education, rural and adult educations are major educational approaches that can be adopted in combating insecurity in the Nigeria society. This is in agreement with a study carried out by Ehi (2009), who in his study noted that education is geared towards developing the individuals for them to live effectively and efficiently in the society and to contribute to its advancement and upliftment. This scenario calls for the intensification of the emphasis on vocational, mass media education, rural education, adult education and entrepreneurial education to equip graduates with occupational survival skills - to be able to identify and even create and exploit investment opportunities that abound in the society. The present global economic crises and rising waves of unemployment have greatly emphasized the need for functional entrepreneurship and vocational education.

This study revealed that the respondents agreed that educational programmes enlightens citizen on dangers involved in insecurity, educational skills makes citizen useful and self-reliance, educational programme exposes citizens to the knowledge of societal developmental in goals, educational programmes like NYSC fosters unity within the Nigerian society and that educational programmes helps to reduce crime within the society. This is in agreement with Rufai, (2013) who noted that education has earlier been defined as a process by which individuals are assisted formally through proper direction and guidance to develop their capacities for their own benefits and that of the society. It therefore follows, by a simple logic, that if a nation bequeaths the right type of education to its citizens, the citizens will not turn against their father- land.

Conclusion

Based on the findings made in this study, conclusions were made that there are insecurities of various shades and hues in different states of Nigeria, borne out of equally diverse causative factors. This paper has identified different national security challenges such as kidnapping, robbery, killing, bombing, among others with its causes as unemployment, bribery and corruption, economic factor, ethnic differences, illiteracy and religious factors are the major factors contributing to insecurity in the Nigeria society. All these threaten the very existence of the nation. The country cannot afford to be indifferent and non- committal to these issues of national security challenges.

It was concluded that vocational education, mass media education, rural and adult educations are major educational approaches that can be adopted in combating insecurity in the Nigeria society. When these are in place, citizens will be more focused and self reliant as they will see themselves as stakeholders in the development of the nation.

The study also concluded that educational programmes enlightens citizen on dangers involved in insecurity, educational skills makes citizen useful and self reliance, educational programme exposes citizens to the knowledge of societal developmental in goals, educational programmes like NYSC fosters unity within the Nigerian society and that educational programmes helps to reduce crime within the society.

Recommendations

In response to the findings made in this study, the following recommendations become imperative that; The government should put in place the necessary educational programmes which will make citizens more useful and self-reliant,

The government should empower their citizens by making provision for citizens to access qualitative livelihood and adequate security of lives and properties,

The security agencies should be empowered and equipped to combat security challenges,

Stakeholders in the education ministry should form a more lasting synergy to guarantee adequate funding of the system since all aspects of the curriculum from time to time need some innovations which introduction is cost intensive.

Regular revision and introduction of innovative curricula such as in Family living Education, Entrepreneurship Education will go a long way to assuaging some of the existing gaps in pupils' acquisition of the right attitude to life and work.

There is need for a review of our education curriculum to include critical subjects that are necessary for development of informed and well rounded citizens. There is no doubt that a good knowledge of certain subjects such as our national history and civics will help in the development of more socially aware youths, truly literate and educated citizens who understand and appreciate the nation's peculiar challenges and can situate themselves within the search for solutions to the problems. Through the curriculum used in our schools, we need to develop citizens that are truly Nigerians at heart and care about the challenges facing our country.

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